

EROSION MODELING OF 2D HOMOGENISED COMPOSITE MODEL

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ICCM 23
INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON
COMPOSITE MATERIALS
BELFAST 2023
30 JULY - 4 AUGUST

INTRODUCTION

➤ **Erosion** – It is the wear process due to the impact of multiple solid particles on the target body.

Figure - 1. Types of Erosion

➤ **Factor affecting Erosion** –

Figure - 2. Erosion Parameters

➤ **Erosion Phenomena**–

Figure - 3. Typical behaviour of Erosion

➤ **Theory of Erosion** –

- Ductile
- Semi Ductile
- Brittle

Figure - 4. Broad Application of Composite Material

➤ **Composite Material** –

- Low density
- High Strength-to-weight ratio
- ➔ Reduces fuel consumption
- ➔ Improves efficiency

➤ Composites made of unidirectional (UD) glass fiber (GF) is highly erosion resistant than any other composite materials.

➤ The 2D woven composites possess better elastic properties over the UD composite. It has better resistance to damage, high toughness, etc.

MOTIVATION

Figure - 5. Degraded Wind turbine blade

Figure - 6. Scaling of Eroder's for Erosion modeling

$$N_s = \frac{m_e v_e^2}{m_s v_s^2} \cdot \frac{A_s T_s}{A_e T_e} \cdot N_e \quad \text{Equation - 1}$$

$$D = N_s \cdot D_1 \cdot \eta_s \cdot \eta_k \quad \text{Equation - 2}$$

Where, N_s = Number of particle to be modeled
 η_s = Substrate property ratio
 η_k = Kinetic energy ratio

Zone A – Damage reduction due to surface degradation
Zone B – Damage reduction due to the interaction of particles
Zone C – Kinetic energy loss due to interaction of particles

Homogenised Composite Model (HCM)

Figure - 8. Composite Model for Erosion Modeling

➤ All five sides of the target body is restrained against deformation except top side.

Material Properties (Woven GFRP)

Limit	Properties	Symbol	Unit	Values
Elastic	Density	ρ	g/cm ³	1750
	Modulus of Elasticity	E_{11}		20.8
		E_{22}		20.8
		E_{33}		8.7
	Modulus of Rigidity	G_{12}		3.92
		G_{13}		4.2
		G_{23}		4.2
	Poisson Ratio	ν_{12}		0.173
		ν_{13}		0.279
		ν_{23}		0.279
Strength	Tensile Strength	σ_{11}		250
		σ_{22}		250
	Compressive Strength	σ_{13}		27.1
		σ_{21}		183
	Shear Strength	τ_{12}		28
		τ_{13}		28

Table - 1. Properties of Material

Convergence Study

Figure - 9. Plot showing Mesh convergence

➤ Mesh size = 17.5 μm (linear brick pattern).
➤ The total number of impacts to be modeled (N_s) is 95804 to match the trend with experimental results.

MODELING

(a). Cumulative mass loss with respect to different impact angles.

(b). The plot showing variation of Substrate Surface Property ratio.

(c). The plot showing variation of Kinetic Energy ratio.

(d). Full-scale prediction of mass loss.

CONCLUSIONS

- Numerical studies have been carried out to predict the erosion of Homogenised composite models (HCM) made with 2D woven Glass fiber composite.
- The maximum mass loss occurs at an impact angle of 30° which shows that the mode of erosion is ductile.
- The model is able to capture the trend of mass loss with experimental results.
- The prediction of mass loss may have a better fit with experimental results if we use a large number of eroding particles.
- The increase in particle-to-particle distance could be another possibility to have a better fit with the experimental results, as interacted particles can cause plastic deformation on HCM.

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OBJECTIVE

ANALYSIS

RESULTS